

THE IMPORTANCE OF PROSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS IN ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MANAGERIAL STAFF

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Abstract: The KPI evaluation system plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of managerial staff in public administration. By improving this system, it is possible to effectively achieve the strategic goals of the state for the future. Therefore, analyzing promising directions for the development of the industry and conducting scientific research is one of the most pressing issues of today.

Keywords: management, evaluation system, KPI, efficiency, digitalization, local governance.

Introduction:

The main task of indicators in the KPI assessment system is to increase the effectiveness of public service, ensure the evaluation of the activities of civil servants based on specific criteria, and establish the rational use of resources. Also, through the KPI evaluation system, government organizations can effectively plan the tasks set and analyze and make effective decisions based on the results achieved.

Literature review:

Currently, regular scientific research is being conducted on the development of the evaluation system in public administration and the identification of future directions. In particular, A.Pujono conducted an analysis of efficiency management systems in the development of local governance [1]. Also, J.Ergashev conducted research on the implementation of the KPI system in improving the mechanisms for assessing the effectiveness of managerial staff [2].

Main part:

The correct implementation of the KPI evaluation system in public administration is one of the necessary issues in increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of managerial staff.

KPI is a tool that allows you to monitor and evaluate the work of people, groups, departments, and companies, helping to assess the implementation of the strategy. [3]

According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 463 dated July 31, 2024, the procedure for assessing the activities of heads and deputy heads of republican and local executive authorities and economic associations was approved.[4] In accordance with this procedure, it was determined that a list of organizations whose activities will be evaluated, performance indicators will be developed and approved, and incentives or disciplinary measures will be taken based on the results.

Some shortcomings may be expected in the full implementation of the KPI assessment system in government bodies and organizations. In particular, first of all, the process of developing KPIs and their formation based on a unified methodology has not yet been fully established. For the full functioning of the KPI assessment system, it is necessary to develop it based on a unified methodology, digitize it, and connect it with the motivation system of civil servants.

It should be noted that a large number and incorrect distribution of performance indicators when assessing the effectiveness of managerial staff, in turn, negatively affects the effectiveness of the organization's activities and the quality of task completion.

In our country, the following areas can be implemented in practice in the future through further scientific research:

- use of innovative technologies in assessment;
- experimental application of the development of methodological manuals in the development of indicators;
- Regular study and assessment of the level of public satisfaction with the results of KPI indicators;
- improvement of the incentive system.

The following proposals have been developed as a promising direction for further research:

- development of training programs for managers of local executive authorities on strategic planning, proper distribution of KPIs, and analysis of results.
- creation of the possibility of analyzing results through artificial intelligence on electronic platforms samaradorlik.uz. [5]

Conclusion:

In our country, by correctly and effectively establishing a system for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of civil servants, in particular, managerial staff, it is possible to achieve savings in time and financial resources.

By increasing the effectiveness and impact of the assessment system, it will be possible to make correct and effective decisions and achieve the practical result of reforms at the grassroots level.

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